

Exploring the Factors Affecting Participation of Pastoralist Girls' Education in Secondary Schools; (The Case of South Omo Zone Secondary Schools (Hamer and Dasanech Woredas), South Omo Zone in Southern Ethiopia Regional State, Ethiopia

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Abstract- The purpose of the study was to explore factors affect girls' participation in secondary education in Dasanech and Hamer woredas, South Omo Zone, South Ethiopia Regional State Ethiopia. The objectives of the study are. - to find out how cultural, school and economic factors affect participation of girls in secondary education, to identify the individual challenges that affect participation of girls in secondary education, to suggest ways of improving girls' participation in secondary education in Dasanech and Hamer woredas. To achieve this, the descriptive survey method was used. The target population of the study was the 2 head teachers of two public secondary schools in South Omo Zone, 20 girls, 20 boys, 10 class teachers. The response rate of the respondents was 100 percent. The study used questionnaires for data collection and collected data were analyzed using computer. The findings from the study showed that socio-economic factors affect participation of girls in secondary education. This resulted to lack of teaching learning materials and lack of personal effects for those with poor socio-economic background. The socio-cultural factors result to early marriages, male preference in family, community initiation into adulthood, negative attitudes of girls in education, cultural practices and feeling of being adults which do affect participation of girls in secondary education. Parents' level of education as a factor affects girls' participation in secondary education because it can promote or lower their participation in education. Educated parents do support their girls in their educational requirements. They also become role models to their daughters' participation in education they most understand what their daughters want and they do provide them with unlike the uneducated parents. Distance from school as a factor has effect on girls' participation in education. The researchers suggest the need to carry out the study to determine other factors affecting girls' participation in secondary education. The researchers also suggest similar studies to be carried out in other woredas secondary schools and in public primary schools in the Zone.

Keywords: Dasanech; Girls participation; Hamer; Pastoralist; South Omo Zone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Education is social activity by which an individual gains knowledge; develop skills, ability, and attitude. It is therefore understood as a basic means of economic, social and cultural changes of a society as a whole. This means it enables individuals and society to acquire the necessary knowledge, skill, and attitude that helps to improve their lives. The responsibility of school principals is to change

things, make things happen, correct things and improve things. The school principals should not only set goals but should also be capable of communicating effectively with teachers. School principals help teachers to embrace goals and to understand the changes that are needed to strengthen teaching and learning and to work towards improvement. When she states that, school principals are required to transform schools into professional learning communities (Harris, 2004:13). Many countries of the world are investing huge amount of resources on education because

improvement in education is important for continuous development, environmental protection, enhancement in maternal and child health.

Education has a great contribution to various developmental sectors, economic, social, cultural, health care and sanitation (Roba, 2006). Education plays a decisive role in improving the living standards of citizens so that nations without basic knowledge and skills might not fulfill the survival criteria in an increasingly knowledge driven world (Liu, 2004).

Education is a fundamental factor in socio-cultural, socio-economic, and political development, as it teaches skills and knowledge in students, preparing them to take up roles in national development (World Bank, 2012). Engine-Demir (2009) stated that education is fundamental to all people regardless of their sex, race or economic status as it is the key to sustainable social, economic and political development.

Secondary education should be given more emphasis since it is the foundation of further system of education. Its main purposes are to produce intellectuals and numerate population that could deal with problems encountered at work and to serve as a foundation on which further education it built. Then, to provide this, the instruction of children at the secondary level is that basic foundation of further education.

Sustainable developments need to be participatory. That is male and female have to participate equals in the process. This equality has to be maintained at all levels of political assignment, economic sectors, educational levels and other social activities. But, in practice we observed that this equality is not maintained. These inequalities seem to be results of unequal participation of female in education.

The Ethiopian Government has taken quite a number of measures, improving the quality of teaching, to enhance female students 'academic performance in particular and realizing the importance of quality education. However, as the government strives to expand education, it also faces the challenge of

ensuring quality, especially for female students. The Ministry of Education in its Education Sector Development Program (ESDP IV 2010/112014/15) document indicates female participation in education is constrained by economic, socio-cultural, family, Environments, personal and school factors.

Statement of the Problem

Even though women play a significant role in the overall development of a nation, they remain under represented at all levels of educational programs, in formal or non-formal education, few receive technical and vocational training and they also account for a very small proportion of enrollment in education both in developed and developing countries (Kelly and Elliott in Kassa, 2006). According to (UNICEF, 2005) the school-related factors such as lack of school facilities and the absence of qualified teachers, distance from the schools, teacher attitudes and teaching practice, all factors influencing academic performance of female students.

A number of studies conducted in Ethiopia regarding the participation, persistence and academic performance of female students both at primary and secondary schools are constrained by several factors. In Ethiopia like other Sub-Saharan countries, economic, social, cultural, school related and institutional factors affect female students of academic performance. Among these, some of the socio-economic and socio cultural factors like, family structure, parental occupation, and parental education, parenting styles, parental attitude, and parental support play a significant role for female academic performance. On the other hand, school related factors such as lack of school facilities and conducive classroom environment, the absence of qualified teachers, distance from the school, teacher attitudes and teaching practice, all affect female academic achievement (Bergman, 2008; Genet, 1998; Yenenesh, 2005; Tesfaya, 2006; Engin demeir, 2009).

The Ministry of Education (MOE, 2004) also reported that the quality of teaching learning process in Ethiopian schools is very low. FDRE, due to some change in government policies, there have been

improvements in female participation in education. However, access to education remains limited and repetition and dropout rate of female students remains high in the Hamer and Dasanech woredas. Consequently, in 2014-2015 E.C the South Omo Zone secondary school leaving examination result also shows that 0% grade twelve students were not passed entrance exam (SOZ administrator). And also shows that 0% grade twelve female students were not promoted to join university. Therefore, to make efforts that improve female participation of pastoralist girls in the secondary schools, this study tried to explore factor affecting the participation of pastoralist girls' students in secondary school of Hamer and Dasanech Woredas.

Objectives of the Study

• General objectives

The main objective of the study is to explore factors affecting pastoral girls' participation in the secondary schools in Hamer and Dasanech woredas.

• Specific objectives

- To find out how cultural, school and economic factors affect participation of girls in secondary education.
- To identify the individual challenges that affect participation of girls in secondary education.
- To suggest ways of improving girls' participation in secondary education in Dasanech and Hamer woredas.

The significance of the Study

Accordingly; the study may be significant in the following;

This study will help woredas Education offices to identify ways to improve pastoral girls' participation or contribute the appropriate measurement and minimize the prevalence of the factors affecting girls' participation and formulating policies pertaining to resources allocation in the improvement of girls' education in Dasanech and Hamer woredas. The study will serve as a source for schools' planners to give attention and take measures to improve pastoralist girls participation in education in general, particular secondary education and it will enable school principals to improve the effectiveness of teaching learning process in the school by providing more than expected supports for pastoralist female

students. It will help to widen the knowledgeable base in students, community, and schools relate to the major factors affecting pastoralist female students. It may help in attitude issues that may motivate and/or serve as an educating material for other researchers and policy makers who are in need to fill the gap in the area. The study may also be interest to all those who concern with the promotion of female education like some non-governmental organizations and other funding agencies working both within schools and within Dasanech and Hamer woredas.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

Research Design

This study employed a survey research design. Sasford (2007) defines survey research as the collection of quantifiable data from a population for purposes of description on identify verifications that may point to casual relationships. This design was appropriate for the study because it captured people's opinion, beliefs and attitudes about factors affecting participation of girls in secondary education. The descriptive survey design was suitable because it involved collection of information, then assessing, finally, describing the data analysis regarding the effect of girls' participation in secondary education.

Population of the Study

The study population consisted of secondary schools in Dasanech and Hamer woredas. For case of subjects, 20 female students, 20 male students, 10 teachers and 2 school teacher heads were selected for the study. This is because such categories of people are expected what causing high cases of low participation of pastoralist girls in secondary schools. From secondary schools for example students experiencing such cases themselves, parents also may be knowledgeable to provide information. All is expected to provide the researchers with reliable data.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Simple random sampling method was used; two secondary schools were selected in Dasanech and Hamer woredas for the study. All the secondary

school names Dasanech and Hamer woredas were written on small pieces of paper, folded, and put in a container and mixed up; two papers were selected at random without replacement. The picked papers were ones from the study areas where the study was conducted from. Two (2) head teachers were selected purposively and 10 teachers corresponding to the number of schools were randomly selected for the study. 20 girls and 20 boys were used for the study, those students who filled the questionnaire adequately and where the rates of low participation of females are high; the study used systematic random sampling. A total of 52 subjects were used in the study.

Sources of Data

To accomplish this study, both primary and secondary data have been applied.

Primary data sources

The primary data used in the study was collected from 20 girls and 20 boys of grade 11-12, 10 teachers and 2 school directors.

Secondary data sources

Secondary data like guidelines, reports, internet, annual statistical abstract collected from sample secondary schools and Woredas education office were used to produce data to compare it with the primary data and to triangulate it.

Data Collection Instruments

Questionnaires

Self-administered questionnaires was constructed Mwesigwa H. (1993) explained that questionnaires are preferred in the study because they give respondents complete freedom of response and are applicable even to the uneducated.

Interview Guide

Interview was conducted to elicit detailed data from the school directors, supervisors and educational officers. In this study the focus of the interview was to understand the experience, perception, interest, views, and difficulties the participants face in secondary education participation. The information obtained from the interview helped what to do next. The participants interviewed within their locality that means the teachers at schools and education officers at the office. The case study was used an interview

guide because this contained a general plan that the interviewers followed.

Documents Analysis

Through the study exercise the researchers made attempts to make a review of the relevant written documents about subject (causes of female dropouts in secondary schools) the document analysis consisted of school records, text books, publication journals, reports presented at conferences, internet, and government documents.

Data Collection Process

The researchers obtained an introduction letter from Jinka University; which was presented to Hamer and Dasanech woredas. The investigators also obtained a letter for Hamer and Dasanech woredas head teachers of the selected secondary schools requesting for permission to carry out research in their schools. The investigators then proceeded to the other respondents to make appointments to start distributing questionnaires and conducting interviews immediately. An appointment was made with the selected respondents to allow them select their own convenient time of participating in the study exercise.

Data Analysis

The data in the study was collected through different tools and analyzed in line with the basic questions raised in chapter one. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were employed to analyze the data. The demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed using frequency, percentage and mean. While data having qualitative nature was analyzed by narration. This qualitative method was chosen because the data were categorized according to themes and objectives in relation to the opinion, views and perception of the respondents.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Introduction

This chapter deals with the analysis, presentation and interpretation of the data collected from grade eleven to twelve students through questionnaires.

Two sets of questionnaires (open and closed) were deployed to 40 students and 10 teachers. And, all the questionnaires were properly filled and returned. On similar manner, semi structured interview guide questions were presented to 2 head teachers.

The analysis and interpretation of the data has been made based on the responses obtained from the respondents. The discussion of the findings focuses mainly on the challenges which affect pastoral girls' participation in the secondary schools in Hamer and Dasanech woredas. Most of the data gathered were organized using table followed by discussions.

Furthermore, the qualitative data gathered from open-ended questions and interviews were used as additional inputs to supplement the discussion.

Questionnaire completion rates

Completion rate is the proportion of the sample that participated as intended in all the research procedures. In this study, all the questionnaires were filled and the response rate was 100 percent.

Table 4.1 - Questionnaires response rate

Category	Distributed questionnaires	Returned questionnaires	Percentage
Girls	20	20	100
Boys	20	20	100
Class teachers	10	10	100
Total	50	50	100

Out of the distributed 50 questionnaires the researchers managed to have a return of 50 questionnaires. This was mainly because the

researchers' approach to the respondents was ethical.

Table 4.2 Distribution of teachers by gender

No	School	Frequency		Percentage	
		Male	Female	Male	Female
1	Dimeka millennium secondary school	21	7	75	25
2	Omo Tefases secondary school	22	3	88	12
	Total	43	10	81.13.	18.87

Table 4.2 indicates that highest proportion of secondary teachers are males 43 (81.13%) and female teachers 10 (18.87%). This was one of the results of the poor participation of girls in secondary education which need to be improved by

the government together with the stakeholders of different schools. Concerning enrolment of girls in secondary schools in Hamer and Dasanech woredas, the result of the research findings were as illustrated in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Enrolment of girls Hamer and Dasenech schools in the year 2025

Class	Hamer			Dasenech			Total		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
Grade 9	101	60	161	55	31	86	156	91	247
Grade 10	34	19	53	17	15	32	51	34	85
Grade 11	40	21	61	30	20	50	70	41	111
Grade 12	43	36	78	33	22	55	76	58	134
Total	218	136	354	135	88	223	353	226	577

Table 4.3 illustrates that the number of girls who were enrolled in grade nine in the year 2025 was the highest compared to other classes. The number kept on going down and the enrolment in grade ten classes was the lowest (34 students) in the year 2025. Table 4.4 illustrates head teachers work experience in their administrative work.

Table 4.4: school directors work experience

Year	Frequency	Percentage
0-2	1	50
3-5	-	-
6 and above	1	50
Total	2	100

Regarding the school directors work experience, those who had served for a period between 0-2 years were 50 percent of the total number same to the number who had served for 6 years and above. Those with less years of work experience turned to be lacking self-motivation thus affecting pastoralist girls' participation in secondary education. Table 4.5 illustrates that more class teachers are male.

Table 4.5: Classroom teachers' response in terms of gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	7	70
Female	3	30
Total	10	100

From data collected on their gender indicate that highest proportion 7 (70%) of the class teachers were male while only 3 (30%) of the teachers were female. table 4.5 shows a big different in gender illustrating that more class teachers were male making the girls to lack role model in their participation in education.

Table 4.6 Professional Training of class teacher

Professional Training	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	6	60
No	4	40
Total	10	100

Out of 10 class teachers in secondary schools in Dasanech and Hamer woredas 6 (60%) had received professional training and 4 (40%) had not received professional training which is an indicator that the number of professionally trained class teachers outweigh those that were not professionally trained and girls were handled mostly by professional class teachers. Table 4.7 illustrates that most of secondary class teachers are graduates (70%) and just a smaller fraction are diploma class teachers.

Table 4.7 Qualification level of classroom teachers

Year	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma	3	30
Degree	5	50
Masters (MA/MSc)	2	20
Total	10	100

Regarding educational qualifications, 5 (50%) of the class teachers were BSc and BA teachers, while 3

(30%) are diploma teachers. The remaining 2(20%) are MA/MSc. The data implies that qualification of class teachers could be a factor that affects participation of girl child in secondary education.

Table 4.8: Classroom teachers' working experience

Year	Frequency	Percentage
0-2	5	50
3-5	3	30
6 and above	2	20
Total	10	100

Regarding work experience, highest proportion of classroom teachers 5 (50%) do not have work experience in the schools, they were in meaning

Table 4.9 Parental source of income

Parents' occupation	Father	Mother	Total	%
Working class	6	3	9	22.5
Self-employee	4	-	4	10
Merchants	3	1	4	10
Pastoralist	8	8	16	40
Unemployed	2	5	7	17.5
Total	23	17	40	100

Results from Table 4.3.1 indicate that the highest percentages of parents in Hamer and Dasenech woreda are pastoralists 16 (40%) and 9 (22.5%) are working class while 7 (17.5%) are unemployed. The

that they were mostly new in those particular schools making them to work hard. They were still a subject to self-motivation to make the girl child to participate in secondary education. Almost 3 (30%) of the classroom teachers had work experience in their schools but only 2 (20%) of the teachers had work experience. This had affected participation of girl in secondary education.

Effect of socio- economic factors on participation of girl child in secondary education

- Parental source of income
Students were required to indicate their parents' source of income or occupation.

remaining 4 (10%) and 4 (10%) are self-employee and merchants respectively. According to Zahrins, (2006) pastoral nomadic move from place to place in search of pasture for their animals. The movements are several kilometers apart. The girl child is always affected whenever their parents move one place to another. It means moving to a new school which may be too far from their new home. Girls tend to start school late or not at all because parents are more concerned for their safety and security away from home.

Personal effects of school directors, girls and boys in participation

Table 4.10 Personal effects of school directors, girls and boys in participation

Response	Frequency		Percentage		Total %
	School directors	Boys and Girls	School directors	Boys and Girls	
Yes	2	29	100	72.5	73.80
No	-	11	-	27.5	26.20
Total	2	40	100	100	100

From the data collected the respondents (school directors, boys and girls) there was relevancy in their

responses making highest proportion (73.80%) to accept that personal effects affect girl child participation in secondary education. None of school

directors and a few of the boys and girls never accepted that it was a factor. This was due to the fact that some of them were having a good socio-economic background enabling them to be getting enough personal effects. Below the researchers wanted to find out if poverty at home had got effect on girls' participation in secondary education. The respondents reacted as tabulated in

Table 4.11. These were 2 head teachers of public secondary schools who were selected.

Poverty at home effect on girls' education

Table 4.11 Poverty at home effect on girls' education

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	2	100
Agree	-	-
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	2	100

Concerning the poverty at home 2 (100%) generally strongly agree that poverty was a factor that affects pastoralist girls participation in secondary education. This was because majority of the parents/guardians were pastoralist/poor and the girls come from very pastoralist/poor homes. As stated by the 2 (two) school directors, it was still found that lack of school affect girls' participation in secondary education as illustrated in Table 4.12.

Lack of school uniform

Table 4.12 Lack of school uniform

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	-	-
Agree	-	-
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	2	100
Strongly disagree	-	-

From the 2 school directors, all disagreed. This meant that all of the school directors do not accepted that lack of school uniform affects participation of girl child in secondary education. From the head teachers it was found that lack of school fees has no

effect on participation of girls in secondary education as tabulated in Table 4.13.

Socio- economy background of pastoralist girls

Table 4.13 socio- economy background

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	70
Agree	3	30
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-

From the classroom teachers there was a clear indication that socio-economic background of the girls affected participation of the girls in secondary education. This was because most girls come from poor homes thus resulting to their school dropouts, their absenteeism and even resulting to unwanted pregnancies and others. From the research carried out from 10 classroom teachers it was discovered that lack of teaching/learning materials affect participation of girls in secondary education. The respondents responded as presented in table 4.14.

Table 4.14 socio- economy background response by students

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	34	85
Agree	6	15
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	40	100

From the boys and girls, there was a clear indication that socio-economic background of the girls affected participation of the girls in secondary education. This was because most girls come from poor homes thus resulting to their school dropouts, their absenteeism and even resulting to unwanted pregnancies and others. From the research carried out from the 20 girls and 20 boys it was discovered

that lack of teaching/learning materials affect participation of girls in secondary education.

Lack of teaching learning materials

Table 4.15: Lack of teaching learning materials

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	19	45.23
Agree	13	30.95
Undecided	2	4.76
Disagree	5	11.9
Strongly disagree	3	7.14

Lack of teaching/learning materials has a lot of effect on participation of girls in secondary school education. The data collected from classroom teachers, girls and boys shows this as illustrated in the table 4.15. Most schools lack computers, books and other necessary teaching learning materials thus making participation of girls in secondary education not to be strongly effective.

Effect of socio-cultural factors on girls participation in secondary education

Regarding the female genital mutilation the 2 school directors and 10 classroom teachers' respondents, stated that female genital mutilation has a little effect on participation of girls in secondary education as table 4.16 shows.

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM)

Table 4.16 Female Genital Mutilation (FGM)

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	-	-
Agree	-	-
Undecided	2	10
Disagree	4	30
Strongly disagree	6	60

As the table illustrates, FGM, the 2 school directors strongly disagree generally that it was not affecting

girl child education. This was also clear with the classroom teachers who also strongly disagree. This means that FGM is not high in the worded. From table 4.17 it is clear that early marriages factor affect participation of girls in secondary education as the table illustrates.

Early marriages

Table 4.17 Early marriages

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	4	33.33
Agree	8	66.67
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-

Table 4.17, regarding the early marriage, all the school directors' and the 8 (66.67%) of classroom teachers agree that early marriages affect the participation of girls in secondary education while 4 (33.33%) strongly agree on it. From table 4.18 below there are illustrations from the data collected from school, girls and boys about male preference in the family.

Male preference in family

Table 4.18 Male preference in family

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	12	100
Agree	-	-
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-

Male/son preference was a factor affecting participation of girls in secondary school. There were some parents who were holding that in their actions even though it was coming down and would fade away that boys were to be given first preference when it came to education. Generally, 100% of the

head teachers and girls were supporting this. This meant that it was not being felt much today. The researchers wanted also to find out how community initiation into adulthood affects girls participation in secondary education. The 20 girls and 20 boys responded as presented in Table 4.19.

Community initiation into Adulthood

Table 4.19: Community initiation into Adulthood

Response	Frequency		Percentage	
	School director	Girls and boys	School director	Boys and girls
Yes	2	35	100	87.5
No	-	5	-	12.5
Total	2	40	100	100

All school directors 2(100%) and highest proportion (87.5%) of girls and boys by ticking "yes" to this activity which meant that it a culture is one the factors affecting girls education in the study woredas. It is taking place higher in the woredas making it to be a factor affecting girls' participation in secondary education. From the table 4.20 it is clear that negative attitude among the girls towards education affect participation of girls in their secondary education.

Negative attitude of girls in education

Table 4.20 Negative attitude of girls in education

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	-	-
Agree	2	100
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	2	100

The researchers wanted to know if negative attitude to girls education affect participation of girls in secondary education. However, Table 4.20 shows, that the two school directors (respondents) agreed

that the girls' attitude made them not to participate in secondary education. Table 4.21 illustrates that sociocultural practices had effect on participation of girls in secondary education from data collected among the respondents.

Socio cultural practices

Table 4.21 Socio cultural practices

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	4	33.33
Agree	7	58.33
Undecided	1	8.33
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	12	100

As from table 4.22 data collected from the school directors and classroom teachers, sociocultural practices, the rate at which they affects participation of girl child participation in secondary education was still high. This was because the community in the woredas was still loyal to their culture to some extent. From the respondents according to Table 4.22, conflict with teachers was not a strong factor that affects participation of girls in secondary education.

Conflict with teachers

Table 4.22 Conflict with teachers

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	11	27.5
Agree	15	37.5
Undecided	2	5
Disagree	7	17.5
Strongly disagree	5	12.5
Total	40	

The researchers wanted to find out if conflict with teachers affected participation of girls in secondary education. Regarding the conflict with teachers, 15 (37.5%) of girls and boys agree while 11(27.5%) strongly agree. 7(17.5%) of boys and girls disagree and 5(12.5%) strongly disagree with conflict with teachers. About 2 (5%) of the girls and boys did not

have a place to place it. This meant that it was a factor and could not be left without consideration. Its effect was averagely felt. It was found from the data collected from 20 girls and 20 boys. Among the 20 girls 20 boys respondents on the study, feeling of being adult had effect on girls' participation, they responded as tabulated in Table 4.23.

Feeling of being adult

Table 4.23 - Feeling of being adult

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	-	-
Agree	11	27.5
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	27	67.5
Strongly disagree	2	5
Total		

Out of 40 girls and boys, 11 (27.5%) of them generally agree/accept this to be a factor affecting girl child participation in secondary school education but highest proportion 27 (76.5%) of them had disagreed meaning that it is not a strong factor. While the remaining 2 (5%) strongly disagree about it.

Effects of parents' level of education on girl child participation in secondary education

- Fathers' and mothers' level of education

From Table 4.24 we find that level of education of the parents is not bad and highest proportion have attained certificate and above education.

Table 4.24 Fathers' and mothers' level of education

Level of education	Frequency		Percentage	
	Father	Mother	Father	Mother
Before class 7/8	3	2	7.5	5
Class 8	5	1	10	2.5
Certificate	12	15	30	37.5
Diploma	6	13	15	32.5
Degree	14	9	35	22.5
Total	40	40	100%	100%

Most fathers/ mothers are educated and only (7.5%) of the fathers had not reached class 7 or 8 and (5%) of mothers same. This is a major contribution on

girls' participation in secondary education. They play a role in support of girl's participation in secondary education.

Table 4.25 indicates that parents' level of education had a lot of effect on girl child participation in secondary education.

Parents level of education

Table 4.25 Parents level of education

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	28	70
Agree	10	25
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	2	5
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	40	100

Parents' level of education is a factor that affects the girl child participation in secondary education. Highest proportion of the respondent 28 (70%) generally agrees that it affects. This meant that educated parents know the need for educating their girls thus improving the girls' level of participation in secondary education. Table 4.26 a lot had been illustrated concerning effects of lack of parents support on participation of girl child in secondary education.

Lack of parents' support

Table 4.26 Lack of parents' support

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	-	-
Agree	2	100
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	2	100

Results from the data collected from the school directors shows that it was a stronger factor. 100% of the respondents accepted. This was a clear indication that parents need to support their girls fully to enable them participate in education. In table 4.27 a lot concerning parents and how they encourage their daughters to participate in secondary education is well illustrated.

Parent encouragements of girls to work hard in school

Table 4.27 Parent encouragements of girls to work hard in school

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	12	30
Agree	21	52.5
Undecided	7	17.5
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	40	100

Highest proportion 21 (52.5%) of the parents, from the data collected from the 40 girls and boys, parents encourage their girls to participate in secondary education. This meant that parents were very positive to girls' education. While 12 (30%) of the respondents strongly agree and the remaining 7(17.5%) of the respondents do not responded. They had known the importance of educating a girl in Hamer and Dasenech woredas.

Effects of distance from school on girls participation in secondary education

The researchers wanted to find out from the respondents the rate at which they agree that girls' insecurity (lack of protection) and distance from school affect girl's participation in secondary education. Table 4.28 deals much with girls' insecurity effects on head teachers' influence on participation of girls in secondary school education.

Girls Insecurity

Table 4.28: Girls Insecurity

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	1	50
Agree	1	50
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	-	-
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	2	100

Out of the 2 school directors, 1 (50%) accepted this to be a factor affecting girls' participation in secondary education. 1 (50%) of the respondent

disagreed with this factor. This makes it to be a factor which highly affects the girl child participation in secondary education.

Concerning table 4.29 distances from school affect girl child participation in education as the table illustrates.

Distance from school

Table 4.29- Distance from school

Rate	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	15	35.71
Agree	19	45.23
Undecided	3	7.14
Disagree	5	11.9
Strongly disagree	-	-
Total	42	100

Highest proportion of the respondents 19 (45.23%) and 15 (35.71% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that distance from school affect girls participation in secondary education respectively. A few of the respondents 5(11.9%) as illustrated table 4.29 disagreed with what the researchers wanted to find out. While the remaining 3 (7.14%) of the respondents do not responded. This was a clear indicator that girls' security was not to the requirement within the woredas. Girl's participation is affected by distance from schools. Majority of the girls cover a long distance as they go to school making them to lack security. Because girls were vulnerable, cases like rape and peer influence may make them be at risk of contracting diseases like HIV/AIDS and other sexually transmitted diseases making distance from school to affect participation of girls in secondary education.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that socio-economic factors affect participation of pastoralist girls in secondary education by causing lack of personal effects, teaching learning materials. It also results to poor payment of school levies and high rate of girl child school drop out. It's also concluded that socio- cultural factors affect girl child participation in secondary education through early

marriages, male preference in the family, and community initiation into adulthood, negative attitude of girl child in education, cultural practices and feeling of being adults.

Parents level of education affect participation of girl child in secondary education by making them to support their daughters in participation in education by providing what their daughters require for personal effects and other educational requirements. Finally distance from school affects girl child participation by making the girl child fatigued after walking, encounter challenges on the way to school like rape, abduction, early marriages, peer pressure and early pregnancies due to lack of security as they travel to school

Recommendations

The study has established that to improve the participation of girls in secondary education, the researchers suggests that the following recommendations;

- The Ministry of Education (MOE) should put in more effort to support pastoralist girls since they are equally needed to participate fully just like boys. This should be done through implementing policies that are already in existence in pastoralist areas. Some of these policies are provision of sanitary pads/towels which the Ministry of Education had committed itself to provide. The enforcement of girls' re-enrolment back to school after delivering babies should also be implemented Tjombonde, 2002.
- The regional and zonal offices should also give priority to buying books, computers and other necessary learning and teaching materials so as to increase girls' participation in secondary schools education. The regional and zonal offices should tally with the five year strategic plan that was set at the onset of free secondary education that every school should have a book ratio of 1:2 and where possible 1:1 by the end of the first five years of free secondary.

- The Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs) should give M.O.E support in provision of girls' personal effects like sanitary pads/towels, school fees and other levies and learning materials like text books for the needy girls for their participation in secondary education. The head teachers (principals) should ensure that in their schools there are female teachers forming 1/3 of the teachers in staff. The female teachers are to act as the role model for the girl child participation in secondary education this female teachers should be sensitized by the principals that they should encourage the girls to participate in education and also tell them the importance of their education for their future.
- The teachers together with the head teachers should sensitize both the boys and the girls that on the side of education all are the same and they need to compete in participation in education with regardless of gender.

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